

STEP 1

- *Provisional listing of opportunistic pathogens/infection presentations*

STEP 2

- *Retrieval of infections in Pharmachild*

STEP 3

- *Adjudication of infections by the SAC*

STEP 4

- *Analysis of the Pharmachild registry*

STEP 5

- *Final evidence-based listing of opportunistic pathogens/infection presentations*